

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B468
 Date: 20 July 2009
 Take Off: 15:36:54Z Basel
 Landing: 19:54:58Z Basel
 Flight Time: 4h 18m 04s

Campaign: CAVIAR
Operating Area: Jungfraujoch

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
5	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
6	Core Chem / NOx	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9	Noxy Training	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
10	SWS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
11	ARIES/FWVS	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
12	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
13	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	Y
14	TAFTS2	Paul Green	Imperial College	
15	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
ViRC chat log	No log available / ViRC not used
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CVI	No log as o operator on CAVIAR
TAFTS	No log taken?

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_154000_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_164000_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_180252_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_190252_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_190425_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_154004_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_180254_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_190422_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_180257_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090720_r0_b468_190419_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B468
 Date: 20/7/09
 Project: CAVIAR
 Location: Jungfraujoeh

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
151556		startup	0.72 kft	244	Basel
151945		tow	0.73 kft	244	
152014		asp open	0.73 kft	244	
152631		taxy	0.73 kft	244	
153654		T/O	0.70 kft	244	
154928	160314	Run 1	16.0 kft	236	
155151		ovhd	16.0 kft	202	NEMOS
160139		ovhd jfj	16.0 kft	119	
160315	160729	Profile 1	16.0 - 19.5 kft	150	
160730	162416	Run 2	19.5 kft	286	
160932		ovhd jfj	19.5 kft	293	
162416	162733	Profile 2	19.5 - 23.0 kft	291	
162733	163721	Run 3	23.0 kft	115	
163606		ovhd jfj	23.0 kft	119	
163743	164140	Profile 3	23.2 - 26.5 kft	080	
164140	165546	Run 4	26.5 kft	290	
164514		sonde 1	26.5 kft	295	
165546	170219	Profile 4	26.5 - 30.0 kft	291	
170219	173215	Run 5	30.0 kft	091	
170654		ovhd jfj	30.0 kft	118	
171406		sonde 2	30.0 kft	278	
171841		sonde 3	30.0 kft	292	
173216	174720	Profile 5	29.9 - 16.1 kft	128	
174308		Profile 5	19.0 kft	237	interrupt
174350		Profile 5	18.7 kft	240	resume
174721	175628	Run 6	16.1 - 16.0 kft	149	
174918		reversing	16.0 kft	138	close to jfj
175628	181641	Profile 6	16.0 - 33.0 kft	292	
181045		ovhd jfj	29.7 kft	117	
181641	182809	Run 7	33.0 kft	262	
181936		Sonde 4	33.0 kft	292	
182154		sonde 5	33.0 kft	293	
183129	183721	Profile 7	33.1 - 35.0 kft	093	
183722	185442	Run 8	35.0 - 35.1 kft	120	
183746		ovhd jfj	35.0 kft	120	
184529		ovhd jfj	35.0 kft	295	
184715		sonde 6	35.0 kft	292	
184920		Sonde 7	35.0 kft	293	
190156	192456	Profile 8	35.0 - 16.0 kft	128	
190841		Profile 8	29.1 kft	260	interrupt
190915		Profile 8	29.0 kft	291	resume
192456	194043	Run 9	16.0 kft	142	
192630		ovhd jfj	16.1 kft	272	
195458		Land	0.71 kft	156	Basel

B468 12:41:45–20:00:43

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B468
Proposed date:	Monday 20 July 2009
Prepared by:	Stuart Newman
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 19 July 2009 1145L (0945Z)

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum. Obtain collocated water vapour profiles with FLASH launch from Payerne expected 2230 L (2030 Z).
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Track between Payerne and Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	7 required. To be released from high altitudes only (FL265 and above).

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

NEMOS = 46° 54.7' N, 6° 54.4' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

B = 46° 27.0' N, 8° 15.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes. Spiral climbs and descents to be started from point S:

S = 46° 43.0' N, 7° 30.0' E

Orientation: Track approx. 116°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

FLASH sounding: Institute of Applied Physics in Bern launch radiosondes from Payerne that are equipped with RS92, Snow White and FLASH-B hygrometers giving the opportunity to measure H₂O reliably between 0 and 35 km. There is also a ground based H₂O radiometer that covers altitude ranges 0-9 km and 30-75 km. Bern perform only nighttime flights, as FLASH-B is an optical instrument that works only at night.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1.	Take off from Basel at 1530Z (1730L)		
2.	Transit to arrive at NEMOS at FL160	0:20	0:20
3.	Perform SLR (NEMOS to B) at FL160	0:10	0:30
4.	Climbing turn to FL195, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	0:35
5.	Perform SLR (B to NEMOS) at FL195	0:10	0:45
6.	Climbing turn to FL230, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	0:50
7.	Perform SLR (NEMOS to B) at FL230	0:10	1:00
8.	Climbing turn to FL265, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	1:05
9.	Perform SLR (B to NEMOS) at FL265, dropping one sonde over JFJ.	0:10	1:15
10.	Straight climb to FL300, finishing at B, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:15	1:30
11.	Perform SLR (B to NEMOS) at FL300, dropping two sondes	0:10	1:40
12.	Turn and perform SLR to point S	0:10	1:50
13.	Spiral descent from FL300 to FL160, starting from point S and drifting with the wind, at 1000 ft/min.	0:15	2:05
14.	Perform first SLR for NOx measurement at FL160 towards JFJ	0:10	2:15
15.	Perform second NOx SLR back towards point S at FL160	0:10	2:25
16.	Spiral climb from FL160 to FL330, starting from point S and drifting with the wind, rate of climb 1000 ft/min.	0:25	2:50
17.	Reposition for run starting at B	0:10	3:00
18.	Perform SLR (B to NEMOS) at FL330, dropping two sondes	0:10	3:10
19.	Straight climb to FL350, finishing at B	0:10	3:20
20.	Perform SLR (B to NEMOS) at FL350, dropping two sondes	0:10	3:30
21.	Perform spiral descent from FL350 to FL160, starting from point S and drifting with the wind, at 1000 ft/min.	0:20	3:50
22.	Return to Basel	0:15	4:05

Mission scientist debrief for CAVIAR flight B468 on 20 July 2009

S. M. Newman

Debrief

The main motivation for this sortie was to obtain coincident profile measurements with a special radiosonde launch from Payerne (arranged by Institute of Applied Physics in Bern, equipped with RS92, Snow White and FLASH-B hygrometers). This was in support of investigations into the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum. NPL solar absorption measurements were made from the Jungfraujoch observatory during part of the flight.

On take-off some cloud was encountered during the climb, with cumulus seemingly capped around 11,000 feet. Patchy cirrus and contrails were prevalent early on in the sortie. Runs were planned to fly between the point NEMOS towards the Jungfraujoch to point B, with an intermediate point S as a starting point for spiral profile manoeuvres.

An initial run from NEMOS at FL160 was made in conditions of significant upper level cloud, with PCASP reporting generally clean air. On approach to the Jungfraujoch it became apparent that the higher peaks and the observatory were shrouded by thick lenticular clouds, which made solar absorption measurements from the mountain sporadic and difficult. Further runs were completed at FL195, FL230, FL265 and FL300, with dropsondes released at the two higher levels. Cirrus coverage overhead was variable (SWS was picking this up well). It was noticeable that FWVS and the General Eastern hygrometers were following each other very well during these runs. The cloud physics kit picked up low concentrations of particles briefly at the highest levels.

A spiral descent from FL300 to FL160 was performed from point S, drifting with the wind and designed to take place as close to Payerne as practicable. Runs at FL160 (useful for Stéphane Bauguitte's NO_x research) were followed by a spiral climb from FL160 to FL330. During the run at FL330 it appeared to be much clearer above compared to earlier in the sortie. A short ascent to FL350 (during which it was noted that the atmospheric humidity at these levels was high) was followed by runs over the Jungfraujoch. Dropsondes were released at FL330 and FL350.

A further spiral from FL350 to FL160 near point S left enough time for one final run at FL160 before the transit back to Basel.

Summary

A very useful intercomparison of water vapour measurements from the aircraft and the FLASH sonde launch which took place at 2250 local time (the FAAM aircraft landed just before 2200 LT). Additionally there was a nearby overpass of the MetOp satellite at just after 2200 LT. The runs at low level are of interest for NO_x research. NPL solar tracking measurements were hampered by cloud cover for much of the flight.

Instrument issues

Large radiometers appeared to operate well, TAFTS experienced some problems at times. FWVS and General Eastern appeared to work very well, responding to changing water vapour concentrations in concert.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: S.M. NEWMAN

Flight No **B468**.....

Date **20/7/2009**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1537	TAKE-OFF				
154410	Transit	FL106	244	47°30, 7°30	Some cloud encountered on transit (2D probes working) Cu seem to be capped ~ 11,000 ft
					Some patchy cirrus/contrails too
154734	Transit	FL143	234	47°15, 7°12	Clear below to port, some Cu to starboard, still patchy upper level cloud
154927	R1	FL160	235	47°, 7°6	Run started before NEMOS
155145	—	Turning	—	46°54, 6°54	NEMOS, repositioning
155334	"	FL160	120	46°48, 7°6	Still significant wispy Cu above
1557					20 per cc PCASP, essentially clear air
160315	end E1	(P1)		46°24, 8°6	Thick lenticular clouds over JFJ area, at FL160 (tops) at end of run
160727	R2	FL195	286	46°24, 8°6	Around 2/8 Ci above, patchy with clear breaks. ~ 6/8 Cu/lenticulars below
161036	"	"	293	46°30, 7°48	Much clearer heading west (below our altitude) but still cirrus above
1620	"	"	292	46°45, 7°0	Still patchy higher level cloud
162220					Turning, not being allowed to climb due to air traffic
162418	P2	FL195↑			20 per litre 2D, wisps of cloud ~ FL210
					Miss. sci. 2 reports precip during turn
162732	R3	FL230	115	46°48, 6°34	Still wispy cirrus at times above
					NPL report cloudy overhead Jungfraujoch
163155	"		118	46°43, 7°30	Seems clearer overhead, still wisps of Ci
163505			118	46°30, 7°34	FWVS and GE following each other quite well, variations in humidity on this run
					More O ₃ , NO _x reported on last run
	P3	FL230↑			Much clearer above
164139	R4	FL265	291	46°24, 8°18	
164410					Wispy cloud near to starboard
164514				46°30, 7°34	Dropsound #1 over Jungfraujoch

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
164830		FL265	292	46°36,7°36	
164910		"			Running under thin cirrus here
165430		"		46°48,7°0	Contrail just to starboard
165546	end run 4	"		46°34,6°48	
	P4	F2265↑			
1657	"	FL277		46°48,6°42	Some Ci around our level
165930					Still some Ci - SWS can see this well
170218	R5	FL300	091	46°42,7°18	(Turning at start) short run to B
170808	end R5			46°24,8°6	Turning, remaining at FL300
171010					Still turning for air traffic horizon is hazy - cirrus, not clear?
171406	R5	FL300			Dropside #2 (just in turn before run)
171539					Turning for repositioning - not SLR?
171837	"	"	291	46°36,7°30	Dropside #3
172230	"	"	290	46°48,7°6	Difficult to say if truly clear above; some cirrus ahead
172450	end R5	"		46°34,6°48	Seems to be cirrus around us SDC, CIP picking up some particles
1730				46°42,7°18	Reposition to S for spiral descent
173205	start P5	FL300 ↓		46°36,7°36	Spiral, drifting with wind; looks relatively clear above here
1743		FL190		46°36,7°36	Interrupt - air traffic constraint
174719	R6	FL160	148	46°36,7°42	Short run toward Jungfranjoch Looks clear above
174908	end	"		46°30,7°54	Terminated early
175200					Running back towards S, turning
175624	end run	FL160 ↑			Spiral climb
	P6				
175926	"	FL194			Lenticular clouds just below and to side
181040	"	FL296	118	46°30,8°0	Broadly clear above, scattered Ci below

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.468**.....

 Date **20/7/09**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1812	P6	FL304	135	46°24,8'06"	(Turning) Hazy on horizon on this heading
181642	R7	FL330		46°24,8'06"	(Turning)
181935		"			Dropsande #4 (late GPS)
					Looking clear above to by eye
182155		"			Dropsande #5
182610	R7	"	292	46°48,7'06"	Difficult to tell if truly clear above, looks clear below near NEMOS
182730					v. thin cloud ahead below our altitude
182809	end R7	"			
183135	P7	FL330 ↑	092	46°42,7'06"	
1835	"	FL344			PCASP up to 750/ce, variable
183620	"	FL347	118	46°36,7'42"	T -50.7, Td -54.6, fairly moist
183720	R8	FL350	120	46°30,7'54"	Short run over JFS
184521					Overhead Jungfranjoch, back towards NEMOS
184714					Dropsande #6 2 mins prior to S
1848	"	"	292	46°36,7'36"	Looks clear above + below here
184919					Dropsande #7
185435					(NEMOS) T -53.3, Td -55.3
1855		FL350	Turn	46°48,6'42"	Largely clear below, looks clear above
190156	P8	FL350 ↓		46°36,7'36"	Spiral descent
190841		interrupt FL290		46°36,7'36"	Brief hold for air traffic
190915		resume FL290 ↓			Looks clear above + below
192303	"	FL175		46°42,7'48"	Getting dark now T -9.8, Td -14.5°C
192453	R9	FL160	142	46°30,7'54"	Turning
192705	"	"	302	46°30,7'54"	SLR from JFS towards NEMOS; some wisps ahead
193416	"	"	280	46°42,7'42"	Patches thin cloud below at times

Cloud Physics Flight Log B468

Date:25/07/09	Operator:PDR	DRS Time:0	DAU1 Time:0	DAU2 Time:0	AUX1 Time:0	AUX2 Time:0
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DAU2 Disk space? 1015 MB

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2			
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y			
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	4.16	Vref (>7V):	7.5	El #1:	2.05	El#1 V (>1):	2.0	Comms?:	Y		
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.17	El #32:	3.57	El#32 V (>1):	1.5				
			Sheath flow	13.8	El #64:	1.92						
			Spectra ok?	Y	Laser current	73.3						

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
												KT made adjustments to SID2 pre flight in an attempt to fix the noise problems. Differences seem minimal but it will be powered today just in case.
09:13:00	ground											SID gave FIFO buffer full errors on startup but after we started taxi these stopped and the concentration dropped from saturated to 1000 counts/sec then fter 2 mins returned to saturated with FIFO full errors
09:27:00												All heaters on
												SID varying from saturated to conc ~10 per s, seems to come down from saturated when in cloud. Not sure if this is due to vibration or because it is actually detecting something.
09:46:55	FL150											Got DAT observed on hotwire for 30 s
11:26:00	FL150											Got DAT observed on hotwire for 30 s
14:07:30												PCASP Heaters off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics	Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref: Flow:	
2DC	EI#1: EI#32:	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V: Flow:	
CDP	Laser V:	
FFSSP	Ref V:	
SID 3	Laser V:	
Rack Equipment		Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B468

Date: 20/7/09

Instruments

1. RFC not operational
- 2.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B468 page 1 of 2

Date: 20/7/09 Operator(s): D. TRADEMAN Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAVIAR SWITZERLAND

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							CN2
							Caviar Madir 2 with 30s
							(CH 30s, N30s, 230s) x ∞
155025	FL160	CN2		0	71	35	Cold Black Body steady cooling!
160330	"	CN2		0	71	31	Stopped script CBB OK. (I'm not sure if HSLC got stopped part way through run ----)
160730	FL195	CN2		0	71	30	
162242	FL195	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
162732	FL230 FL230	CN2		0	71	31	Start
163755	FL230	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
164143	FL265	CN2		0	71	30	Start.
165550	FL265	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
170230	FL300	CN2		0	71	31	Start
170838	FL300	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
171330	FL300	CN2		0	70	31	Start over JFK in turn!
172504	FL300	CN2		0	71	30	stop @ Bit of track adjustment where we were going
173140	FL300	CN2		0	71	31	Start
174722	FL160	CN2		0	71	30	Start
174956	FL160	CN2		0	71	30	Stopped for turn
175133	FL160	CN2		0	71	30	
175625	FL160	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
181644	FL330	CN2		0	71	30	Start
182848	FL330	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
183720	FL350	CN2		0	71	30	Start
183853	FL350	CN2		0	71	30	Stopped turn
184358	FL350	CN2		0	71	30	Re started
185445	FL350	CN2		0	71	31	Stopped

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	20/07/09	Flight	B468	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	CAVIAR	
Departure			Arrival		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on					at time	1350	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	25°C	Ch 17	25°C	Ch18	25°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on					at time	1350	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time		
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software					at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

B468_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

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14:02:49.10 --- - - -
14:02:49.10 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:02:49.10 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:02:49.10 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B468
14:02:49.10 --- - - -
14:03:01.51 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:03:01.60 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:03:01.68 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:03:16.11 --- - - - *** Operator: Stuart Rogers
14:03:29.40 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:31.78 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:33.09 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:37.40 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:03:40.32 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
14:03:43.19 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:03:45.55 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
14:03:52.10 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
14:03:55.28 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
14:04:05.37 --- - - - Reset shutters.
14:27:30.68 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
14:27:37.72 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:27:44.67 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 117.990
14:27:46.34 SWS 118.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
15:10:09.55 SWS 118.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:10:11.24 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
15:18:12.81 --- - - - Reset shutters.
15:18:27.87 LSH - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
15:18:27.94 SWS - - 50 100 Dark measurement started.
15:18:27.96 USH - - 50 100 Dark measurement started.
15:18:29.32 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:18:29.52 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:18:29.72 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:20:44.12 SWS - - 50 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:20:44.32 USH - - 50 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:20:44.57 LSH - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:20:52.71 --- - - - *** Taxiing
15:39:12.66 --- - - - *** T/O 15:37-ish
15:41:03.71 --- - - - *** In cloud
15:41:57.78 USH - - 50 100 Dark measurement started.
15:41:57.89 LSH - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
15:41:57.90 SWS - - 50 100 Dark measurement started.
15:41:59.26 USH - - 50 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:41:59.47 LSH - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:41:59.66 SWS - - 50 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:46:27.23 SWS - - 50 100 Dark measurement started.
15:46:28.68 SWS - - 50 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:46:32.38 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:46:34.33 SWS - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
15:46:35.77 SWS - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
15:49:29.83 --- - - - *** FL160
15:52:43.10 SWS - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:52:46.42 USH - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:52:49.35 LSH - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:53:26.75 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
15:53:35.25 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:53:53.97 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:54:12.68 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:54:31.45 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:54:50.23 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:55:09.04 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:55:27.73 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:55:46.47 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:56:05.11 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:56:23.27 SWS - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:56:23.91 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:56:42.62 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

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15:57:01.35	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:57:20.19	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:57:38.78	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:57:57.54	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:58:16.49	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:58:35.23	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:58:53.95	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:59:12.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
15:59:31.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:59:49.96	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:00:08.62	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:00:27.33	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:00:41.76	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
16:00:41.78	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:00:41.81	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:00:43.20	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:43.41	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:43.68	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:46.07	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:01:04.90	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:01:23.56	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:01:42.19	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:02:01.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:02:19.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:02:38.54	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:02:57.38	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:03:16.16	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:03:35.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:03:53.80	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:04:12.56	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:04:29.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:04:31.46	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:04:50.26	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:05:09.09	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:05:27.85	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:05:39.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** Lost SWS NIR
16:05:43.04	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:05:43.09	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
16:05:43.13	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:05:44.54	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:44.70	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:44.96	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:46.71	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:05:51.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:06:05.32	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:05.54	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:06:07.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:06:12.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
16:06:22.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:06:24.32	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:06:24.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:06:32.00	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:36.03	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:06:36.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:06:37.54	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:42.32	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:06:42.98	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:06:46.00	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:06:47.46	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:01.78	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:07:11.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS NIR is back after reinitialisation
16:07:20.75	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:07:39.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL195
16:07:39.59	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:07:58.56	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:08:17.36	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:08:36.14	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:08:54.98	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:09:13.90	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

16:09:32.68	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:09:51.31	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:10:10.11	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:10:29.02	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:10:47.76	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:11:06.57	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:11:25.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:11:44.13	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:12:03.01	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:12:21.92	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:12:40.81	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:12:59.58	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:13:18.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:13:37.15	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:13:55.87	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:14:14.70	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:14:33.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:14:52.33	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:15:11.07	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:15:19.20	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
16:15:19.23	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:15:19.26	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:15:20.71	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:15:20.87	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:15:21.11	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:15:29.89	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:15:48.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:16:07.65	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:16:26.36	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:16:45.17	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:17:03.78	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:17:22.71	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:17:41.63	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:18:00.62	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:18:19.43	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:18:38.26	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:18:57.15	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:19:16.03	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:19:35.02	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:19:54.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:20:12.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:20:31.82	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:20:50.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:21:09.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:21:28.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:21:47.44	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:22:06.34	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:22:25.10	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:22:43.67	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:23:02.36	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:23:21.29	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:23:40.30	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:23:59.34	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:24:18.38	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:24:37.35	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:24:56.36	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:25:15.37	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:25:33.90	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:25:52.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:26:11.75	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:26:30.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:26:49.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:27:08.24	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:27:27.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:27:34.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL230
16:27:46.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:28:05.10	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:28:24.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:28:43.04	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

16:29:02.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:29:20.60	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:29:39.68	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:29:58.73	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:30:12.27	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:30:12.36	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:30:12.96	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
16:30:13.98	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:14.13	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:14.77	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:17.27	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:30:36.26	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:30:48.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** Lost SWS NIR again
16:30:54.81	SWS	54.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:31:00.30	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:31:01.75	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:04.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:31:09.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
16:31:13.79	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:31:18.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:31:21.84	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:28.31	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:31:28.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:31:29.83	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:32.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:31:32.79	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:31:35.88	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:31:37.34	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS NIR is back
16:31:51.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:32:10.25	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:32:28.95	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:32:47.57	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:33:06.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:33:25.34	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:33:44.38	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:34:03.40	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:34:22.04	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:34:40.74	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:34:59.31	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:35:17.93	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:35:36.49	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:35:55.10	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:36:13.71	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:36:32.28	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:36:51.22	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:37:09.80	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:37:28.46	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:37:44.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:37:47.49	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:38:06.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:38:20.89	---	-	-	-	-	***
16:38:25.59	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:38:44.62	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:39:02.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:39:03.13	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:39:22.08	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:39:41.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:40:00.09	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:40:18.60	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:40:37.65	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:40:56.26	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:41:14.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:41:33.52	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:41:40.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL265
16:41:52.10	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:42:10.71	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:42:29.32	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:42:47.88	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

16:43:06.43	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:43:25.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:43:44.00	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:44:03.15	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:44:22.18	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:44:40.74	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:44:59.38	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:45:17.95	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:45:26.60	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:45:26.67	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
16:45:26.77	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
16:45:28.06	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:45:28.28	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:45:28.55	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
16:45:36.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:45:55.42	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:46:14.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:46:33.19	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:46:52.09	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:47:10.72	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:47:29.85	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:47:48.43	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:48:06.99	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:48:26.03	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:48:44.66	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:49:03.72	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:49:22.25	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:49:41.03	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:49:59.57	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:50:18.11	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:50:36.63	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:50:55.24	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:51:13.77	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:51:32.33	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:51:50.87	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:52:09.83	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:52:28.48	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:52:47.14	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:53:05.76	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:53:24.43	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:53:43.07	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:54:01.67	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:54:20.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:54:39.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:54:58.06	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:55:17.15	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:55:35.67	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:55:54.31	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:56:13.26	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:56:31.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:56:50.44	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:57:09.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:57:27.64	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:57:46.17	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:58:05.25	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:58:23.92	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:58:42.71	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:59:00.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:59:01.76	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:59:20.50	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
16:59:37.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:59:39.01	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:59:57.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:00:15.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
17:00:16.55	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:00:34.11	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:00:34.11	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
17:00:34.14	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:00:34.44	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.

17:00:34.92	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:00:35.44	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:00:35.96	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:00:36.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:00:36.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:00:40.92	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:00:43.33	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:00:52.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
17:00:53.99	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:01:12.67	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:01:31.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
17:01:31.25	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:01:49.93	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:02:08.70	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:02:27.25	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:02:32.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL300
17:02:44.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
17:02:46.35	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:03:04.93	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:03:23.69	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:03:42.34	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:04:00.97	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:04:19.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:04:38.23	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:04:56.88	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:05:15.54	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:05:34.25	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:05:53.04	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:06:11.84	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:06:30.50	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:06:49.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:07:08.04	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:07:26.67	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:07:45.30	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:08:03.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:08:22.68	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:08:41.46	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:09:00.11	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:09:18.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:09:37.44	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:09:56.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:10:15.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:10:33.62	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:10:52.35	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:11:11.00	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:11:29.83	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:11:48.37	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:12:07.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:12:25.83	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:12:44.41	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:13:03.11	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:13:21.91	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:13:40.57	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:13:59.28	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:14:18.07	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:14:36.69	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:14:55.52	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:15:14.25	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:15:33.11	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:15:51.15	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:15:51.22	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:15:51.23	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
17:15:51.70	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:15:51.81	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:15:51.93	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
17:15:52.72	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:15:53.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:15:53.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:16:02.28	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.

17:16:04.54	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:16:10.38	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:16:29.10	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:16:47.95	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:17:06.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:17:25.51	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:17:44.22	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:18:02.91	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:18:21.90	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:18:40.78	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:18:59.53	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:18.13	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:19:36.73	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:55.58	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:20:14.18	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:20:33.00	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:20:51.68	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:10.23	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:21:28.95	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:47.69	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:22:06.47	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:22:25.17	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:22:43.96	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:23:02.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:23:21.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:23:40.07	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:23:58.80	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:24:17.54	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:24:36.48	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:24:55.37	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:25:14.18	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:25:33.04	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:25:51.85	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:26:10.72	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:26:29.51	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:26:48.36	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:27:07.34	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:27:26.04	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:27:44.87	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:28:03.42	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:28:22.04	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:28:41.02	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:28:59.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:29:18.67	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:29:37.30	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:29:55.97	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:30:14.82	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:30:33.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:30:52.24	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:31:10.91	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:31:18.94	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:31:19.01	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:31:19.02	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
17:31:20.50	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:20.63	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:20.86	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:29.72	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:31:48.50	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:32:07.54	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:32:26.52	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:32:32.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** Spiral descent from FL300
17:32:45.36	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:33:04.09	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:33:23.01	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:33:41.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:34:00.52	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:34:19.42	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:34:38.22	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:34:56.89	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

17:35:15.43	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:35:34.22	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:35:51.16	SWS	44.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:35:56.27	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:46:43.03	USH	-	-	50	100	Dark measurement started.
17:46:43.07	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:46:43.07	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:46:44.60	USH	-	-	50	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:46:44.85	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:46:45.04	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:46:57.86	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:46:59.88	USH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
17:47:01.37	USH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
17:47:24.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL160
17:47:34.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:35.08	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
17:47:45.01	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:45.73	SWS	51.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:46.48	SWS	46.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:47.19	SWS	42.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:47.95	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:48.69	SWS	33.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:49.44	SWS	28.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:50.18	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:50.95	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:51.71	SWS	15.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:52.43	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:53.19	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:53.93	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:54.67	SWS	-2.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:55.43	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:56.18	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:56.97	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:57.72	SWS	-20.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:58.48	SWS	-25.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:59.22	SWS	-29.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:47:59.96	SWS	-34.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:00.71	SWS	-38.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:01.45	SWS	-43.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:02.20	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:02.98	SWS	-51.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:03.73	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:48:22.77	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:48:41.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:49:00.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:49:18.97	SWS	-54.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:49:37.84	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:49:56.76	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:50:15.54	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:50:34.44	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:50:53.28	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:51:12.08	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:51:30.86	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:51:49.88	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:52:08.61	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:52:27.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:52:46.40	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:53:05.01	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:53:23.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:53:42.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:54:01.77	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:54:20.79	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:54:39.61	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:54:58.62	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:55:17.57	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:55:36.40	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:55:55.15	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:56:13.92	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:56:32.87	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

17:56:51.72	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:57:10.75	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:57:29.68	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:57:48.63	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:58:07.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:58:26.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:58:45.16	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:59:03.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:59:23.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:59:41.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:00:00.88	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:00:18.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
18:00:20.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:00:38.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:00:52.26	USH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:00:52.31	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:00:52.34	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:00:53.79	USH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:00:54.01	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:00:54.30	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:00:57.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:01:16.97	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:01:35.95	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:01:54.89	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:02:13.71	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:02:32.26	SWS	-54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:02:51.09	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:03:09.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:03:28.98	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:03:47.79	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:04:06.79	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:04:25.69	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:04:44.61	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:05:03.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:05:22.36	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:05:41.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:06:00.29	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:06:12.54	SWS	-16.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
18:06:16.32	SWS	-16.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
18:15:30.63	USH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:15:30.69	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:15:30.76	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:15:32.09	USH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:32.29	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:32.52	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:38.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:15:38.54	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
18:15:48.70	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:49.40	SWS	50.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:50.17	SWS	45.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:50.90	SWS	40.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:51.67	SWS	36.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:52.42	SWS	31.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:53.18	SWS	27.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:53.93	SWS	22.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:54.69	SWS	18.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:55.43	SWS	13.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:56.19	SWS	9.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:57.02	SWS	4.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:15:57.78	SWS	-0.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:15:58.55	SWS	-4.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:15:59.30	SWS	-9.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:00.02	SWS	-13.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:00.78	SWS	-18.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:01.54	SWS	-22.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:02.30	SWS	-27.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:03.06	SWS	-31.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:03.81	SWS	-36.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:04.53	SWS	-40.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

18:16:05.28	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:05.99	SWS	-49.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:06.75	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:16:25.29	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:16:43.88	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:17:02.69	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:17:21.25	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:17:39.82	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:17:58.81	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:18:17.38	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:18:36.36	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:18:55.49	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:19:14.06	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:19:33.00	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:19:52.06	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:20:10.71	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:20:29.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:20:48.70	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:21:07.77	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:21:26.49	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:21:45.49	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:22:04.54	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:22:23.55	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:22:42.46	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:23:01.02	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:23:20.03	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:23:38.61	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:23:57.18	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:24:16.22	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:24:27.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** SZA and heading both approx 292.5deg
18:24:34.85	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:24:45.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** SAA not SZA!
18:24:53.40	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:25:12.08	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:25:30.89	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:25:49.96	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:26:08.61	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:26:27.26	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:26:46.14	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:27:05.19	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:27:24.24	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:27:42.85	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:28:01.84	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:28:20.51	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:28:39.10	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:28:57.63	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:29:16.61	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:29:35.62	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:29:54.21	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:30:12.75	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:30:31.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:30:38.94	USH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:30:39.00	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:30:39.00	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:30:40.45	USH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:30:40.63	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:30:40.94	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:30:50.43	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:31:09.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:31:27.78	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:31:46.86	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:32:05.56	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:32:24.63	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:32:43.25	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:33:01.85	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:33:20.94	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:33:39.69	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:33:58.63	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:34:17.21	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

18:34:35.78	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:34:54.38	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:35:13.41	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:35:32.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:35:50.77	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:36:09.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:36:28.53	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:36:47.10	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:37:05.67	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:37:23.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL350
18:37:24.67	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:37:43.20	SWS	54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:38:01.75	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:38:20.33	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:38:38.93	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:38:58.05	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:39:16.96	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:39:35.91	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:39:54.54	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:40:13.17	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:40:32.27	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:40:51.28	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:41:10.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:41:29.34	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:41:48.40	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:42:07.52	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:42:26.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:42:45.26	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:43:04.34	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:43:23.24	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:43:41.95	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:44:00.52	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:44:19.06	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:44:37.75	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:44:56.42	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:45:15.31	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:45:33.94	SWS	-55.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:45:44.08	LSH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:45:44.11	USH	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:45:44.17	SWS	-	-	100	100	Dark measurement started.
18:45:45.57	LSH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:45.77	USH	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:45.99	SWS	-	-	100	100	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:52.54	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:46:11.08	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:46:29.65	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:46:48.22	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:47:07.28	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:47:25.89	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:47:44.55	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:48:03.34	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:48:21.90	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:48:40.46	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:48:59.23	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:49:17.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:49:36.96	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:49:55.66	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:50:14.35	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:50:33.01	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:50:51.56	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:51:10.18	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:51:28.74	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:51:47.39	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:52:06.36	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:52:24.96	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:52:43.64	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:53:02.56	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:53:21.17	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:53:39.86	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

```

18:53:58.78 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:54:17.46 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:54:36.02 SWS 54.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:54:54.55 SWS -54.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:55:13.45 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:55:32.31 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:55:51.22 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:56:09.99 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:56:28.78 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:56:47.31 SWS -54.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:57:06.02 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:57:24.67 SWS -54.8 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:57:43.42 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:58:02.20 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:58:20.98 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:58:39.58 SWS -54.6 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:58:58.28 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:59:16.97 SWS -55.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
18:59:35.55 SWS 54.6 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
18:59:54.42 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:00:13.26 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:00:31.92 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:00:50.79 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:01:09.56 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:01:28.40 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:01:46.95 SWS -54.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:01:52.11 --- - - - *** Telescope seems slightly juddery turning
CW from -50 to -55deg?
19:02:01.17 --- - - - *** Or am I imagining it?
19:02:05.80 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:02:22.50 SWS - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:02:22.53 USH - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:02:22.57 LSH - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:02:24.01 SWS - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:02:24.31 USH - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:02:24.42 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:02:24.49 LSH - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:02:43.19 SWS 55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:03:02.00 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
19:03:20.76 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
19:03:28.44 SWS 11.2 - - - Telescope stopped.
19:03:33.57 SWS 11.2 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:04:00.72 --- - - - *** Spiral descent(?)
19:07:28.86 --- - - - *** Re: judder comment above - CCW not CW
19:08:51.36 --- - - - *** Telescope is cold enough for slight liquid
condensation.
19:11:03.52 --- - - - *** Picking up aircraft strobe on USH?
19:17:21.29 SWS - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:17:21.35 LSH - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:17:21.37 USH - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:17:22.82 SWS - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:17:23.07 LSH - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:17:23.22 USH - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:17:49.66 USH - - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:20:39.62 LSH - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:20:41.12 LSH - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:20:42.48 LSH - - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:20:54.96 SWS - - - 100 100 Dark measurement started.
19:20:56.45 SWS - - - 100 100 Manual scene recording started.
19:23:30.75 SWS - - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:24:33.94 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 122.196
19:24:35.14 SWS 113.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
19:25:01.46 --- - - - ***
19:25:06.28 SWS - - - - - Idling
19:25:08.93 USH - - - - - Idling
19:25:11.20 LSH - - - - - Idling
19:25:16.46 LSH - - - - - Instrument closed.
19:25:18.11 USH - - - - - Instrument closed.
19:25:21.23 SWS - - - - - Instrument closed.

```

```
19:25:24.72 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.  
19:26:07.52 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...  
19:26:07.65 SWS - - - - Telescope motor control quit.
```